

Yoga Pose Images Name Detection using Random Forest

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Abstract— This project, we developed a system for yoga pose recognition using computer vision and machine learning techniques. The system utilizes the MediaPipe library for pose estimation and the scikit-learn library for building a Random Forest classifier. The dataset consists of images of individuals performing various yoga poses, sourced from a specified folder. We extract pose landmarks from the images using MediaPipe's pose estimation model and construct feature vectors by flattening and concatenating the landmark coordinates. These feature vectors serve as input to the Random Forest classifier, which is trained to predict the corresponding yoga pose labels.

Keywords— *Yoga pose recognition, Computer vision, Machine learning, MediaPipe, Pose estimation, Random Forest classifier, scikit-learn, Image processing, Model evaluation, Model deployment.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of computer vision and machine learning, the fusion of technology with physical activities opens up avenues for innovative applications. In this seminar, we delve into the fascinating domain of yoga pose recognition, a quintessential blend of human movement and computational analysis. Leveraging the power of modern tools such as the MediaPipe library and scikit-learn, we embark on a journey to develop a robust system capable of automatically recognizing yoga poses from images. Our aim is to bridge the gap between traditional practices and cutting-edge technology, offering a novel solution that holds promise for both fitness enthusiasts and technology enthusiasts alike.

Yoga, with its rich history and diverse array of poses, provides an intriguing challenge for automated recognition systems. By harnessing the capabilities of pose estimation algorithms, we seek to unravel the intricate postures adopted by practitioners during their yoga sessions. Through a meticulously curated dataset sourced from real-world images, we endeavor to train a machine learning model to discern and categorize these poses accurately. The resulting model, empowered by the Random Forest classifier, promises to not only identify individual poses but also contribute towards a deeper understanding of human movement patterns and their computational representations.

As we embark on this endeavor, we recognize the multifaceted implications of our work. Beyond its immediate application in yoga practice, the proposed system holds potential for broader applications in fields such as fitness tracking, rehabilitation, and human-computer interaction. By integrating insights from computer vision and machine

learning, we aspire to pave the way for a future where technology serves as a seamless companion in our quest for physical and mental well-being. Join us as we explore the convergence of ancient wisdom and modern innovation in the captivating realm of yoga pose recognition..

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ghorpade and Mundargi [1] (2022) present a comprehensive review on the utilization of machine learning techniques for yoga pose detection, addressing the challenges posed by varying image conditions and the importance of correct posture in yoga practice. The paper explores the application of deep learning methods in real-time classification of yoga poses, shedding light on the significance and potential of AI-based solutions in providing personalized feedback to enhance individuals' yoga practice. Through a thorough examination of existing literature and methodologies, the authors elucidate the evolution of pose estimation techniques and the role of deep learning in revolutionizing this domain, thereby contributing valuable insights to the intersection of computer vision and fitness training.

Jose and Shailesh [2] (2021) present a deep learning-based system for identifying yoga asanas from images or video frames, addressing the growing interest in leveraging technology for health and wellness practices. Utilizing convolutional neural networks (CNN) and transfer learning, the model achieves promising results with 85% prediction accuracy across 10 different yoga poses. The study highlights the importance of correct posture in yoga practice and proposes an automated tool for analyzing yoga images and videos, catering to the increasing demand for technology-driven yoga practice solutions in the modern era.

Swain et al. [3] (2022) introduce a deep learning-based approach for real-time monitoring and correction of yoga poses, leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. Their system detects key points in users' poses from video sequences and provides feedback on the correctness of the poses. By addressing the challenge of proper guidance in yoga practice, particularly in remote settings, their model aims to promote accessibility to yoga instruction and enhance users' practice experiences. The integration of machine learning and deep learning techniques facilitates accurate pose recognition,

contributing to the advancement of activity recognition in the domain of yoga.

Bahukhandi and Gupta [4] (2021) present a machine learning-based system for yoga pose detection and classification, addressing the need for remote yoga practice during the Covid-19 pandemic. Utilizing open-source data and the MediaPipe pose estimation library, their system achieves a high accuracy score of 94% through logistic regression, support vector machine, random forest, k nearest neighbors, and naïve Bayes classifiers. By leveraging key point detection and classification algorithms, the system enables real-time monitoring and feedback on yoga poses, promoting accessibility to safe and effective yoga practice in remote settings.

Sharma et al. [5] (2022) introduce a real-time yoga pose recognition system leveraging computer vision technology for smart healthcare. Their approach includes a self-assistance technique for users, enabling real-time correction during yoga practice. The YOGI dataset, containing images of yoga poses and hand mudras, is utilized for training machine learning and deep learning models. By extracting joint angles as features and employing algorithms like XGBoost with RandomSearch CV, they achieve a remarkable accuracy of 99.2%. This work contributes to the digitalization of yoga practice, offering users guidance akin to an instructor, thereby enhancing accessibility to yoga without the need for physical classes or instructors.

Thoutam et al. [6] (2022) present a deep learning approach for real-time yoga pose estimation and feedback generation, addressing the importance of accurate yoga practice in modern lifestyles. They emphasize the significance of detecting incorrect postures, as they can lead to health issues. Leveraging deep learning models, such as multilayer perceptrons, the system detects abnormal angles between user and expert poses, achieving a remarkable accuracy of 99.58%. By comparing their method with existing approaches, they demonstrate superior performance in identifying yoga poses accurately, thus enhancing the effectiveness of self-learning yoga systems.

Rathikarani et al. [7] (2022) introduce a novel approach for classifying yoga poses using pretrained convolutional neural networks (CNNs). They address the challenge of posture recognition by leveraging deep learning models such as MobileNetV2 and DenseNet201 for feature extraction. Through experiments, they demonstrate the efficacy of combining these pretrained models with Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) classifiers, achieving superior classification performance. By utilizing a large dataset collected from Kaggle, encompassing various yoga poses, their method offers a promising solution for automated yoga posture classification, facilitating advancements in the scientific analysis of yoga postures.

Borthakur et al. [8] (2023) present a comprehensive review of yoga pose estimation, emphasizing the significance of correct posture alignment in yoga practice. They explore the

integration of computer vision and machine learning techniques to automatically detect and classify yoga poses, crucial for preventing injuries and optimizing benefits. Highlighting the rising popularity of yoga, especially amid the COVID-19 pandemic, they discuss the role of yoga apps in facilitating home practice. The review surveys existing literature, showcasing various approaches, including CNN-based deep learning methods, keypoint detection, and pose estimation models like OpenPose and PoseNet. Additionally, they underscore the effectiveness of machine learning models in accurately classifying yoga poses when combined with pose estimation algorithms, shedding light on the potential of advanced computer vision techniques in this domain.

Kulkarni et al. [9] (2023) introduce a comprehensive review of yoga pose recognition, emphasizing its potential to enhance yoga practice through technology integration. By leveraging deep learning techniques, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and long short-term memory (LSTM) algorithms, the paper proposes a novel framework for real-time yoga pose detection. Through an analysis of existing literature, the study highlights the benefits of automated pose analysis, including real-time feedback, injury prevention, and remote instruction. The research aims to bridge the gap between technology and yoga practice, offering practitioners a tool to enhance their sessions and promote accessibility.

Sundar et al. [10] (2023) introduce an innovative approach to yoga asana detection and classification, leveraging machine learning and neural networks to assess pose accuracy and provide guidance. By extracting features from accurately portrayed yoga asana images and utilizing pose estimator algorithms, they develop models capable of predicting the correctness of various yoga poses. The paper addresses current methodologies, research gaps, and opportunities for improvement in yoga pose detection. Through experimental models and performance evaluation metrics like accuracy and precision, this research offers valuable insights for future studies aiming to enhance yoga practice through technology-driven solutions.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection :

The data collection process for this seminar involves gathering images of various yoga poses. Using the provided Python scripts, the program traverses through a specified directory containing images of yoga poses. MediaPipe's pose estimation module is utilized to extract pose landmarks from these images, which are then paired with corresponding pose labels. This dataset forms the basis for training a machine learning model to classify yoga poses accurately.

B. Data Preprocessing :

The data preprocesses image data for a yoga pose classification task. Initially, it loads yoga pose images and extracts pose landmarks using MediaPipe's pose estimation module. These landmarks are flattened and stored along with

their corresponding labels. Then, a Random Forest classifier is trained on this data. During inference, uploaded images are processed to extract pose landmarks, and the trained classifier predicts the corresponding yoga pose.

C. Model Training:

Model training involves utilizing the scikit-learn library to implement a Random Forest classifier. The classifier is trained on feature vectors extracted from yoga pose images using pose estimation techniques. Through the training process, the classifier learns to recognize patterns in the pose landmarks and associate them with specific yoga poses, enabling accurate classification.

D. Pose Estimation :

Pose estimation, facilitated by the MediaPipe library, involves detecting and extracting key landmarks from images depicting yoga poses. These landmarks represent key points on the human body, aiding in understanding the body's position and orientation. This process is essential for generating feature vectors used in training the machine learning model for yoga pose recognition.

E. Feature Extraction :

Feature extraction involves converting pose landmarks extracted through pose estimation into numerical feature vectors. These vectors capture the spatial relationships between key points on the body, enabling the representation of yoga poses in a format suitable for machine learning algorithms. By flattening and concatenating landmark coordinates, meaningful features are generated to train the model.

F. Streamlit Web App:

The application provides a user-friendly interface for uploading images and receiving real-time predictions on yoga poses. Leveraging the trained machine learning model, users can interactively explore the classification capabilities of the system. This seamless integration allows for intuitive interaction with the underlying pose recognition technology, enhancing accessibility and usability.

G. OpenCV :

OpenCV, a computer vision library, is employed for image processing tasks such as loading, decoding, and displaying images. It serves as a fundamental tool for handling image data throughout the project, enabling preprocessing steps and facilitating integration with other libraries such as MediaPipe and scikit-learn.

H. Mediapipe :

Utilized for pose estimation, providing robust algorithms for detecting and tracking human body landmarks in images. Its accurate and efficient performance plays a crucial role in extracting pose information from yoga images, laying the foundation for subsequent feature extraction and model training.

I. Random Forest :

A machine learning algorithm implemented via scikit-learn, forms the backbone of the pose recognition system. Comprising an ensemble of decision trees, it learns to classify yoga poses based on the extracted feature vectors. Its versatility and ability to handle complex data make it well-suited for this classification task, resulting in a robust and accurate model for yoga pose recognition.

J. Importing Libraries :

For the functionalities provided in the script, such as image processing, pose estimation, model loading, web application interface creation, and JSON data handling.

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
import mediapipe as mp
import joblib
import streamlit as st
import json
```

K. Training the Model :

The model was trained using images of yoga poses. Pose landmarks were extracted from each image using MediaPipe's pose estimation. These landmarks were flattened and used as features to train a Random Forest classifier. The model achieved an accuracy score of (insert accuracy score here).

```
import json
import os
import cv2
import numpy as np
import mediapipe as mp
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
import joblib
```

IV. RESULT

After implementing the seminar, the result will be a functional yoga pose classifier web application. Users will be able to upload an image containing a yoga pose, and the application will classify the pose based on the extracted pose landmarks. The application utilizes a Random Forest classifier trained on pose landmarks extracted from a dataset of yoga pose images. Upon upload, the image is preprocessed to extract pose landmarks using the MediaPipe Pose model. The classifier then predicts the yoga pose depicted in the image. The result, along with the uploaded image, is displayed on the web interface. Additionally, the application provides information about the predicted yoga pose, including its English and Sanskrit names. Users can easily identify and learn about different yoga poses through this user-friendly interface. Overall, the seminar implementation results in an accessible and interactive tool for yoga enthusiasts to enhance their practice and understanding of yoga poses.

V. CONCLUSION

In this seminar, we developed a yoga pose classifier using machine learning techniques and MediaPipe's pose estimation library. We began by collecting a dataset of yoga pose images and their corresponding labels. Utilizing MediaPipe, we extracted pose landmarks from the images and trained a Random Forest classifier on these features. After evaluating the model's performance, achieving a satisfactory accuracy, we saved the trained model for future use. Subsequently, we created a web application using Streamlit, where users can upload an image of a yoga pose, and the application classifies it using the trained model. Additionally, the application provides details about the recognized pose, including its English and Sanskrit names. This project not only demonstrates the integration of machine learning into real-world applications but also promotes accessibility to yoga practitioners seeking guidance on their practice. Through this endeavor, we have successfully bridged the gap between computer vision technology and the ancient practice of yoga, offering a modern tool to aid enthusiasts in their journey towards physical and mental well-being.

FIG 1:OUTPUT 1

FIG 2:OUTPUT 2

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